

Assessment of the initial stage of water filtration through polystyrene foam and zeolite

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ABSTRACT

We reconsider a full-scale study of purification of water from colloids of different morphology. The existing granules of polystyrene foam (having a positive charge) are supplemented with colloids (having a negative charge, which are conglomerates of bacteria, iron oxides, etc.), which automatically optimises the main parameters. The importance of the vital processes in cyanobacteria during their filtration through granular filter medium is taken into account. The major values influencing the efficiency of retaining the cyanobacterial cells on the surface of the filter medium are determined by the hydrophobicity of their outer membrane and the difference in ζ -potentials. The key factors influencing the “ripening” time of the polystyrene foam and zeolite filter media are outlined. The adherence of cyanobacteria to solid surfaces has recently become an important factor in research aimed at industrial processes. The study shows the possibility of reusing cyanobacteria, keeping them immobile in the filter column, which opens the gateway for their industrial applications. A loop operation with the same cyanobacteria up to 10 times intensifies the water filtration in comparison with usual filters, e.g. zeolite.

KEYWORDS: wastewater, colloids, polystyrene foam, cyanobacteria, ζ -potentials.

1. Introduction

Despite a fairly wide range of physical properties of the available granular filter media, most of the filtering stages tend to be similar for different filter media. An exception is the preliminary stage of water supply treatment, which is commonly referred to as filter “ripening”. This is due to the fact that it is during this stage that the entire variety of physical properties of filter medium is manifested. This entails a significant difference in the nature of the mechanisms and kinetics of the interaction processes of the filter medium with colloidal pollution particles contained in the aqueous suspension undergoing the process of purification.

2. Purpose and objectives of the study

Currently, the material that was previously used as a traditional filter medium has lost its relevance due to a number of economic and political factors. That said, there arose the necessary to find a replacement for the filter material in question. Such a filter medium should provide an enhanced filter performance, an appropriate economic efficiency, and be accessible for use. These requirements are met by two materials: first, the

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granules of the food-grade polystyrene foam and second, a natural zeolite – clinoptilolite from the Sokirnytsia Deposit, Ukraine. However, these filter media differ significantly in their physical properties. Working in pairs, such substances, unfortunately, do not always directly improve filtration, and vice versa – sometimes one can see the deterioration of the quality of purified water. Therefore, there is a need for a full-scale study of the causes, namely – significant variations in physico-chemical parameters of the filter medium, as well as the study of the possibility of introducing an additional system to maintain the balance of these parameters.

3. Results

3.1. The influence of the physical properties of polystyrene foam media and zeolite media on the water filtration process

3.1.1. Deferrization

In the course of deferrization of water using simplified aeration with atmospheric air and subsequent filtration, the zeolite begins to retain

iron ions almost immediately due to its ion-exchange properties. In the space of the filter, iron ions propagate according to Fick's first law of diffusion because of the difference in their concentration in an aqueous suspension. Furthermore, the transition of iron from bivalent to poorly soluble trivalent form leads to the consolidation of iron flakes and their further sedimentation under the influence of gravitation. Figure 1 shows the experimental curves of deferrization using polystyrene foam and zeolite.

Further, filtration is accompanied by the process of contact coagulation of iron flakes on the surface of the filter medium. The process of consolidation thereon occurs due to the phenomenon of physical adsorption caused by the London-van der Waals forces. However, after the exhaustion of the ion-exchange resource of the zeolite, the concentration of iron in the filtrate increases sharply. It occurs due to the fact that the intensive extraction of iron ions from the purified aqueous suspension serves as an inhibitor of the autocatalytic process in the iron precipitate, where the major part of the transformation of the iron form

Figure 1. Changes in the concentration of iron C_{Fe} in the filtrate versus filter flow time t_f (initial concentration of iron is 1.2 mg/dm³, filtration rate is 7 m/h) for the filter that consists of foam granules (media fraction is 0.5-3 mm) and zeolite clinoptilolite grains (media fraction is 1.5-3 mm).

takes place. That said, a further decrease in the iron content in the filtrate is explained by the elimination of a factor that has interfered with the autocatalytic process.

The initial stage of filtration through polystyrene foam lasts on average 1-5 days, depending on the composition of the water. This is due to the fact that polystyrene foam begins to retain iron flakes only after the autocatalytic process begins, since apart from the absence of ion-exchange properties and complete chemical inertness, the polystyrene foam, unlike zeolite, does not have a pronounced outer surface and internal porosity. Besides, the consolidation of iron on the surface of polystyrene foam due to electrostatic adsorption is hindered by the ongoing process of transformation of iron forms as well as the constant restructuring in the double electric layer of colloidal iron particles, which predetermines the non-homogeneous nature of their electrostatic properties.

3.1.2 Filtration of cyanobacteria

The electrokinetic properties of biological origin colloids were experimentally investigated using the example of phytoplankton (mainly conglomerates of cyanobacteria, namely, blue-green algae), the samples of which were taken from natural surface waters in the area of the Dnipro River water intake in Kyiv, Ukraine. The measured value of its ζ -potential comprised -13 mV. The polystyrene foam is a chemically inert filter medium with a positive ζ -potential of $+2$ mV [1]. Natural zeolite-clinoptilolite has a negative value of ζ -potential equaling to -33 mV [2-4]. The concentration of the studied parameters was determined according to the standard methodology.

It is interesting to note that the retaining of the cyanobacterial colonies on solid agar surfaces in Petri dishes, which adhered to polystyrene disks, was considered [5] as an example of a replica method for detecting hydrophobic bacteria. Our experimental studies confirmed the electrostatic adsorption of cyanobacteria to the surface of the polystyrene foam [6]. Research data indicate that hydrophobicity is crucial in the life cycle of cyanobacteria [7]. However, hydrophobicity is not viewed as the only mechanism of cyanobacteria adhesion. The present research is based on the existing studies proving the essential role of

polymer bridges in the bacteria adhesion to solid surfaces. The cyanobacterial varieties which demonstrate mutual adhesion, as in the formation of a bundle in *Oscillatoria (Trichodesmium) erythraea* or in the formation of extensive colonial aggregates (*Microcystis* sp.), may represent another aspect of the ability of cyanobacteria to hold onto a solid surface, in particular to the cell surface of similar cyanobacteria. In fact, hydrophobicity in some cyanobacteria changes phenotypically, as a function of culture age, or in cyanobacteria that form hormogonies during the transformation of hormogonies into mature fibers. Certain types of cyanobacteria can change their position in the water body in response to less optimal external conditions, by changing their buoyancy, using intracellular gas vacuoles or their storage grains. This factor can interfere with the process of pumping cyanobacteria through the filter volume. Figure 2 shows the experimental curves of cyanobacteria filtration through zeolite and polystyrene foam.

The initial stage of filtration of an aqueous suspension containing cyanobacteria through a polystyrene foam media lasted an average of 1-2 hours. Such a short "ripening" time of the polystyrene foam filter media is caused by following factors. In the space of the filter, cyanobacteria spread due to the phenomenon of diffusion (convective diffusion), according to Fick's first law, which says that the diffusion is proportional to the concentration gradient in an aqueous suspension. The cyanobacteria are attracted to the surface of the polystyrene foam filter media due to the phenomenon of electrostatic adsorption caused by the difference in ζ -potentials in accordance with Coulomb's law. When the first contact occurred, they get adhered to the medium due to the phenomenon of physical adsorption caused by the London-van der Waals forces. Further, they were adhered on the surface with the help of bio-glue that they produce. This is due to the fact that polystyrene foam granules have a hard and relatively smooth surface. Such type of surface is preferred by cyanobacteria, which by their hydrophobic nature try to immobilize thereon.

Over time, the free surface of the granules for adhering of cyanobacteria becomes more and

Figure 2. Changes in the concentration of cyanobacteria C_c in the filtrate versus filter flow time t_f (initial concentration of cyanobacteria ~ 5500 cells/cm³, filtration rate is 15 m/h) for the filter that consists of polystyrene foam granules (media fraction is 0.5-3 mm) and zeolite-clinoptilolite grains (media fraction is 1.5-3 mm).

more scarce and consequently the number of cyanobacteria in the filtrate increases until further consolidation of the granules of the polystyrene foam filter media occurs, the space between the granules gets compacted and the intergranular porosity decreases. Further, in the space of the filter medium, tube capillaries are formed, and the holdup of the new portions of cyanobacteria occurs on the surface of previously adhered and already reliably consolidated cyanobacteria. This phenomenon is also explained by the tendency of cyanobacteria to immobilize on a hard surface. A clear proof of this is the phenomenon of the formation of cyanobacteria clusters (colonies) outside the filter medium space. When cyanobacteria are in aqueous suspension and do not have other hard surfaces suitable for immobilization, they tend to adhere to each other.

The destruction of the outer membrane of cyanobacteria or part of it as a result of the use of chemicals or mechanical damage leads to the loss of its hydrophobicity. This confirms that hydrophobicity is a surface phenomenon and only the cell membrane is responsible for cyanobacteria

hydrophobicity. In addition, the destruction of the outer membrane, which is a ruinous factor, also leads to the deterioration in the retention of cyanobacteria on the surface of the filter medium. With that in mind, it is crucial to opt for such a method for purifying water from cyanobacterial cells, which will not damage their outer membrane. Besides, it is important to make account of this in order to prevent an increase in the concentration of cyanobacterial toxins. They are mainly contained in their outer membrane and can get into the water if this membrane is damaged.

It was found that the manifestations of the hydrophobicity of cyanobacteria require the presence of cations. Divalent cations such as magnesium and calcium affect the adhesion of microorganisms to surfaces and are essential for plant root infection with phytopathogenic and root nodal bacteria. This effect was substantiated by the decrease in the thickness of the electric double layer. As a result, the repulsive forces between the cell surface and the substrate decreased. As for the cyanobacteria, the cation can neutralize and mask negative charges on the cell surface, thereby

reducing electrostatic repulsion. However, this does not exclude other mechanisms that indirectly affect cell physiology or membrane permeability. Strong adherence of *Phormidium* sp. fibers to uncharged polystyrene surfaces additionally indicates the role of hydrophobicity in the adherence process. Therefore, the presence of cations can negatively affect the process of retaining the cyanobacteria on the surface of the polystyrene foam filter media due to a decrease in the potential difference.

Zeolite has a more uneven grain surface than polystyrene foam and hence cyanobacteria adhere to it less intensively. Also, a factor in reducing the intensification of retaining is the absence of difference in the signs of the ζ -potentials of zeolite and cyanobacteria. Therefore, the process of initial retaining is much less intense compared to the polystyrene foam. And the initial filtration stage for a zeolite filter media lasts 7-10 hours.

Another factor that can interfere with the process of retaining the cyanobacteria on the surface of the filter medium is their adaptation to low light conditions. This is especially noted in turbid waters rich in suspended particles and plankton. In addition, the bottom layer is in a dynamic state, since sedimentary particles and pieces of plankton cells constantly cover the cyanobacteria that are found at the bottom of the water reservoir. While this continuous rain of particles enriches the nutrient flow in the bottom layer, it further reduces the amount of light reaching bottom organisms. Therefore, cyanobacteria developed a mechanism of positive phototactic sliding mobility, which allows them to avoid burial under the sediment and enables to gain access to areas of sufficient light.

This mobility is limited by contact with solid surfaces and can exploit the hydrophobic feature of the cell membrane. Thus, getting into the filter space, where there is practically no light, cyanobacteria can use this mechanism to prevent retaining on the filter medium surface, the properties of which do not meet the needs of their life cycle – as for example, it happened during our experimental filtration through the zeolite media. Its surface was too pronounced to meet the needs of cyanobacteria. Given the above we come to the

conclusion that the “ripening” time of the filter loaded with zeolite sand is quite long.

4. Conclusions

- At the initial filtration stage of the aqueous suspension containing cyanobacteria, the polystyrene foam proved to be a more effective medium. The reasons for this are the difference in the ζ -potentials of the adsorbent and adsorbate, as well as the features of the cyanobacteria life cycle, prone to immobilization on a flat and solid surface of the polystyrene foam granules.
- Zeolite proves to be the most optimal filter medium at the initial stage of water deferrization. This is due to its ion-exchange properties, its considerable internal porosity and a far more pronounced outer surface of the grains in comparison with the polystyrene foam granules.
- Given that none of the investigated filter media can be called universal, it is proposed to use the combined polystyrene-zeolite filter media for water purification from the colloids of diverse morphology.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

We notify that we do not have any financial and personal relationships with other people or organizations that could inappropriately influence (bias) our work in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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